

Alternative ways of European participatory organic
fruit breeding projects

The apple tree germplasm bank of SERIDA

SERIDA

InnOBreed

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SERIDA - Regional Agrifood Research and Development Service

SERIDA is the Regional Agrifood Research and Development Service of the Asturias region in the north-west of Spain. The service develops and implements research projects for the improvement of the Asturian agri-food sector and was founded in 1984 in the facilities of the Villaviciosa Pomological Station.

In SERIDA's Fruit Growing Research Program, research is carried out aiming at the generation of knowledge and efficient fruit management models that are compatible with environmentally friendly agriculture. The Apple Tree Germplasm Bank was developed by a Fruit Growing Research Program that started in 1989, including all accessions belonging of the Pomological Station of Villaviciosa (1956-1983). The facilities of the Fruit - Apple Research Program and most of the collection plantations of the Apple Tree Genebank are located at the SERIDA headquarters in Villaviciosa. Although there are also two collection orchards in two other locations in Villaviciosa, one in Priesca and the other one in Oles.

The Asturias region has an important cider apple-production. Cider production is the third most important sector within the agri-food sector. The current production of cider products can be estimated at approximately 45 million litres of natural cider and 40 million litres of sparkling cider, filtered cider and juice. The cider apple production is \approx 45 million kg in odd years and \approx 15 million kg in even years.

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The conservation and valorisation of Asturian apple plant genetic resources

The Fruit-Apple Research Programme of SERIDA carries out prospecting and conservation of the Asturian apple diversity (cider and dessert cultivars), as well as evaluation, characterisation, selection, breeding and valorisation of local apple cultivars.

Main results of the activities conducted by the Fruit-Apple Research Programme of SERIDA can be summarised as follows

- 22 local cider apple cultivars selected by SERIDA with good production, partial resistance to Scab, low susceptibility to Mildew, European canker and Monilia and good rusticity, after a process of evaluation in orchards of collaborating growers, and included in Asturias cider PDO. Twelve of these cultivars are currently the most widely used.
- 34 other local cultivars characterised by SERIDA with technological interest were also included in Asturias cider PDO.
- Some local table apple cultivars have also rusticity and quite good agronomic performance.
- More than 1200 ha of new semi-intensive orchards with cultivars selected by SERIDA are cultivated without sprays or low protection.
- Implementation of the Protected Designation of Origin Asturias cider as an important contribution to ensuring the use of a valuable resource such as local cider apple varieties and the cider apple orchards of the region.

InnOBreed collaboration

Since 2022, SERIDA is part of the InnOBreed project as a case study, joining a network of European colleagues working in the same field.

The participation in the InnOBreed project implies an important contribution to the activities of SERIDA. The exchange of information between all participants of new methodologies being developed in the InnOBreed project will contribute to incorporate improvements in the processes of characterisation, evaluation and selection of cultivars available in the Apple Germplasm Bank.

Furthermore, SERIDA as an InnOBreed case study is also contributing importantly to the objectives of this Horizon Europe project. Some of the methodologies developed for the characterisation, evaluation and selection of varieties available in the Apple Germplasm Bank by the Fruit - Apple Research Programme are of interest for the development of the InnOBreed project. Also, the management itineraries of the germplasm bank collection plantations under organic growing conditions, with low inputs and without fungicide treatments against diseases will be useful for the InnOBreed project.

More information about SERIDA can be found here:
<http://www.serida.org/>

To find out more, you can also contact Enrique Dapena de la Fuente: edapena@serida.org

